

FIUSIS, A BIOMASS POWER PLANT FUELLED EXCLUSIVELY BY OLIVE TREE PRUNINGS. A CASE STUDY IN THE AGROINLOG H2020 PROJECT

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ABSTRACT: In the framework of the AGROinLOG H2020 Project, the Research Centre for Engineering and Agro-Food processing of CREA was in charge of supporting the birth of a new olive tree prunings-based energy chain in the Greek Region of Fthiotida (Central Greece), with particular regard to the pruning harvesting phase. Despite the huge areas of olive grow plantations, such bioenergy chains have never taken off anywhere in the Country. On the contrary in Italy there are several practical examples of pruning utilization for energy purposes. Among these, the 1 MWe plant active in Calimera (Lecce), named Fiusis, is the first biomass power plant in the world to use exclusively olive tree prunings as a fuel source. Fiusis has been identified as a reference model to be followed in the organization of the production chain to set up in Greece. This paper reports the key elements that allowed Fiusis to achieve the success highlighting its environmental, economic and social integration with the local territory. The main technical elements of the biomass plant, the supply chain management and the operational parameters of the harvesting machineries are described. Moreover, the first achievements obtained in Greece in transferring the “Fiusis model” are reported.

Keywords: bioenergy, biomass, agricultural residues, biopower plant

1 INTRODUCTION

For a long time 2020 year has represented the reference date for important goals for the protection of our planet. Many of these goals have been achieved, but new and more ambitious goals have been set in the EU 2030 framework for climate and energy policies [1]. Bioenergy is expected to contribute greatly with around 50% of overall renewable energy production, but in a more sustainable way [2].

According to this scenario, the European policy for energy limits the use of biomass crops for energy purposes, promoting the utilization of agroforestry residues and by-products [3].

In Italy these guidelines are transposed in the new support scheme that incentives greatly small-scale biomass plants supplied with residues and by-products (Decre 23 June 2016 on non-photovoltaic RES).

In this framework the exploitation of agricultural residues is crucial in the development of a sustainable bioenergy. Among the agricultural residues, prunings residues are a good quality feedstock hugely available [4]. In Europe pruning biomass available yearly is more than 13 million tons; about 80% are located in the Mediterranean area and most of them in Italy and Spain [5]. In Italy, only olive groves make available more than 2.6 Mt pruning biomass yearly [6]. According to Acampora et al. [7] up to 7 tonnes per hectare per year of green prunings are available in Apulia Region where about 33% of the Italian olive groves are concentrated [8].

Although it is an abundant biomass resource, the exploitation of tree prunings for energy purposes is still limited. On the contrary, prunings are usually disposed through open-air burning which is a costly practice and environmental harmful [9].

From some years now, in the area surrounding Calimera municipality (Lecce) in Southern Italy the olive tree prunings are no more a disposal problem. Since 2010 a 1MWe biomass plant fueled exclusively with local olive tree prunings is running. The power plant, called Fiusis from the ancient Greek word “Physis” meaning “Nature”,

is a unique in Europe circular economy model turning agricultural waste into energy [10].

Fiusis plant became a case study in the framework of the AGROinLOG Project (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No 727961), aimed at demonstrating the technical, environmental and economic feasibility of Integrated Biomass Logistic Centres (IBLC) for the development of new value chains based on agricultural waste and by-products.

Within the AGROinLOG Project, the Italian partner CREA - Research Centre for Engineering and Agro-Food processing, was in charge of supporting the birth of a new olive tree prunings-based energy chain in the Greek region of Fthiotida (Central Greece), with particular regard to the pruning harvesting phase.

Despite huge olive groves areas, these bioenergy chains have never taken off anywhere in the Country [11]. On the contrary in Italy there are several examples of pruning utilization mainly for heating, either for household or for industrial purposes.

Among these examples, Fiusis plant is the only one to use exclusively olive tree pruning to produce electricity and heat. Due to its uniqueness, Fiusis plant has been identified as a reference model to analyze and show in order to support the organization of the new production chain in Greece where moreover the climatic characteristics and crop management are very similar to that of the southern Italy.

Two technical visits for Greek partners were organized to show them first-hand the plant characteristics, the harvesting systems running, and the supply chain organization adopted by Fiusis.

Moreover, experimental trials were performed both in Italy and Greece in order to evaluate the performance and work quality of the machines involved in the pruning harvesting.

After the involvement in the AGROinLOG Project, Fiusis became a “Flagship success case” in the uP-Running Project (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No 691748) as the first known case of small-scale power plant using only olive tree prunings as fuel [12].

Recently, Fiusis was selected as “Innovative Business Case” in the Rubizmo Project (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No 773621) winning among hundreds of screened business initiatives the “Rural Business Innovation Award” in the “Bio-Based Value Chains Category” for having contributed to raising the environmental awareness in rural communities and for having created new job opportunities in an area with the highest unemployment rates in Europe [13].

This paper reports the key elements that allowed Fiusis to achieve the success highlighting its environmental, economic and social integration with the local territory. It is summarized the company history through the words of its owner in facing the barriers and the obstacles, such as technical knowledge acquiring, challenging authorization procedure tackling, local consensus building, seeking funding.

The main technical elements of the biomass plant, the supply chain management and the operational parameters of the harvesting machineries are described. Moreover, the first achievements obtained in Greece in transferring the “Fiusis model” are reported.

2 FIUSIS INITIATIVE START UP

As claimed by the administrator of the Fiusis plant Marcello Piccinni during the technical visits organized for the Greek partners of the AGROinLOG Project, his business idea was born from the observation that in some area of the Mediterranean, like in Italy, Greece and Spain, people live in real forests of olive trees. Despite this, prunings have never been exploited before for any purposes, but they were usually field burnt with uncontrolled pollutants emissions.

On the contrary, the huge availability of prunings could be sustainably used like the forestry biomass in Tyrol, Carinthia and Bavaria regions is used for energy production in biomass plants well integrated with the surrounding territory.

Before starting the initiative, even more than finding the necessary funding, two elements were crucial: the acquisition of technical know-how and the identification of the supply basin.

Four years of study were necessary to acquire all the technological knowledge related to the productive process and for the identification of the best site for the plant.

A supply basin of 9 municipalities in a 10 km area around Calimera municipality was identified (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The supply basin of Fiusis plant

The technical knowledge acquired have been fundamental in providing the guarantees required by some financial institutions that have economically supported the construction of the 8 million euros' plant.

Moreover, the technical expertise allowed to overcome the bureaucratic obstacles in order to obtain the authorizations and to respond to all those who were against the initiative from the start. The effort to build consensus locally and engagement of local farmers was decisive to start up the plant and then to the development of the supply chain.

3 THE SUPPLY CHAIN ORGANIZATION

Initially the harvesting of the prunings was outsourced to contractors with high and unsustainable costs. After three years, a subsidiary company of Fiusis, named Ligna, was set up aimed exclusively to harvest and supply the prunings to the plant.

Ligna receives the requests by farmers interested in supplying the prunings. The geographic coordinates of the fields, the number of olive trees and the date of pruning are recorded and processed in order to manage the harvesting and delivery to the plant.

Two types of harvesting systems are used: four towed shredders (Facma mod. Comby TR200) for small olive groves (less than 400 trees) and a stationary chipper (Caravaggi mod. BIO900) for bigger olive groves (more than 400 olive trees).

Chipping in both cases is carried out after about one-month period in which the prunings are left in the field to ensure drying and leaf shedding. After chipped, the prunings are temporarily stored at farms fields. According to the needs of the biomass plant, the prunings are taken from the fields until the scheduled collection, guaranteeing a constant supply during the whole year. In this way biomass loses humidity in the fields more quickly, and the area for storage at the plant is consequently relatively small in size (2,400 m²) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Storage area at the plant

No remuneration is provided to the farmers that instead have the advantage of having pruning's residues removed from the field avoiding costs for disposing practices (such as burning or mulching).

The increasing involvement of farmers and their increasing awareness to contribute in turning agricultural waste into useful energy resource has pushed more and more farmers to be part of the project. In few years the requests for the harvesting of olive grove prunings have gone from the initial 12 to the present 1,200.

At present, it is estimated that the open-air burning practice has decreased inside the supply basin by 70%.

4 THE BIOMASS PLANT DESCRIPTION

The biomass plant has a sheltered storage area that acts as a buffer between the in-field storage and the daily needing of the plant. From here about 25 tons of prunings a day are transferred to the boiler loading system. The loading system made of rakes and conveyor belts allows to handling biomass with irregular size (called hog fuel). The irregular size of biomass, usually a problem for smaller plants, in the Fiusis plant generates two advantages: a better natural drying during the storage and a better primary combustion in the boiler.

All the plant technology is entirely made in Italy. The main components are a moving grate boiler of 4.4 MWth capacity (engineered by Uniconfort Srl) and a turbine based on the Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) of 1 MWe power capacity (engineered by Turboden S.p.A.).

Figure 3: Moving grate boiler of 4.4 MWth capacity (engineered by Uniconfort Srl)

Figure 4: ORC turbine of 1 MW power capacity (engineered by Turboden S.p.A.).

Considering 8,000 operating hours per year, the plant produces 8,000 MWh annually delivered to the national grid; the amount is equivalent 35% of Calimera's daily and 100% of its night-time needs.

Furthermore, thanks to an innovative filtering system (made of 30 multicyclone filters and 702 stainless steel mesh filters) (designed by ABB Italia S.p.A.) the fine particle emissions is only 1 mg/Nm³, well under the legal limit (set at 30 mg/Nm³).

From a social point of view the production chain activated by Fiusis has contributed to local employment creation. Six technicians oversee the functioning of the plant, while 15 workers are organized in three teams for the collection and one for the delivery of the biomass to the plant.

Finally, two new production lines are next to start by exploiting residual heat and ashes. Residual heat will be

recovered to dry other wood residues and produce wood pellets, while ashes will be used to make biofertilizers.

5 HARVESTING SYSTEMS DESCRIPTION AND TRIALS IN ITALY AND GREECE

In addition to the organization of the technical visits at Fiusis plant and in-field demonstrations of the harvesting machines in operation, CREA carried out a dedicated prunings harvesting test in order to provide the main technical details of the harvesting systems used by Ligna, such as working times, fuel consumption and the quality of the biomass shredded.

Two types of harvesting systems were analysed: a towed shredder used for small olive groves with less than 400 trees and a stationary chipper used for bigger olive groves with more than 400 olive trees.

Facma Comby (Model TR200) is a shredder towed by tractors with at least 56 kW (75 hp). The pick-up system located on the front of the machine has 2 m working width. The rear dumpster has a capacity about 5 m³. The machine can shred pruning until 8 cm diameter (Figure 5).

Caravaggi BIO900 is a stationary chipper 9.65 m long, 3.90 m high and 10,000 kg weigh. The machine can shred biomass until 45 cm diameter. A tractor with a fork collects the prunings pushing them into a heap near the chipper. A hydraulic crane powered by a tractor grabs the branches to be unloaded into the chopping machine's feeding system (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Harvesting with towed shredders (Facma mod. Comby TR200) for olive groves with less than 400 trees

Figure 6: Harvesting with a stationary (Caravaggi mod. BIO900) for bigger olive groves

The results achieved must to be analyzed bearing in mind the main differences between the two harvesting systems, such as the different number of machines involved and the related costs and the differences between the olive groves characteristics where the tests were

performed (different field shape and biomass yield).

In the case of the shredder, turning time at the end of the rows and the time needed to discharge the shredded material from the 5m³ dumpster, have strongly affected the overall harvesting efficiency. The effective field capacity (including pauses and turning times) was about half of the theoretical field capacity (0,90 ha h⁻¹) [14].

On the contrary the stationary chipper presented a very high harvesting efficiency with an effective field capacity slightly lower than the theoretical field capacity (0.61 ha h⁻¹), because the chipper could work continuously since the fork accumulated material without pauses.

The stationary chipper was more productive than the shredder; the material capacity was respectively 7.26 t h⁻¹ (pruning yield 12.08 t ha⁻¹) for the stationary chipper and 3.20 t h⁻¹ (with pruning yield 4.36 t ha⁻¹) for the shredder.

The hourly fuel consumption of the whole system made of the stationary chipper and the two tractors (for the fork and for the crane) was 2.5 times higher than the consumption of the shredder (about 10 l h⁻¹). But referred to the biomass shredded the fuel consumption of the stationary chipper system was only 3,5 l t⁻¹ while only the tractor that towed the shredder consumed 5 l t⁻¹.

In light of these results and following the feelings by the Greek farmers that attended the demo-days it was decided to transfer and test the shredder system in Greece.

So, in April 2018 field tests were conducted evaluating the shredder performances in Agios Kostantinos (Fthiotida Region, Greece), both in hilly and flat-slope olive grove fields (respectively about 50% of the municipality territory). The results were very interesting from both economic performances and biomass quality points of view [15].

Figure 7: Agios Kostantinos (Fthiotida Region, Greece)

After the preliminary tests, an extensive pruning harvesting demonstration was carried out by Greek Project partners CERTH (Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas) and INASO (Instituto Agrotikis kai Sinetairistikis Oikonomias). The aim was to evaluate a real pruning value chain in terms of performance (working times, yield), economics (fuel consumptions, logistics costs) and environmental sustainability (GHG emissions) [11].

The demonstration lasted for 14 days. Around 232 wet tons were harvested from 53.8 ha (126 olive groves).

The harvester consumed 17.2 litres of diesel per hectare (5.3 litres per dry ton of harvested prunings), while 8.8 litres of diesel per hectare were consumed for biomass haulage from the fields to the storage area by two trailers (2.7 litres per dry ton of harvested prunings).

About 0.69 hectares of olive groves were harvested per hour (without considering breaks). The average net harvesting efficiency during the demonstration was at 2.2

dry tons per hour.

Daily results showed how local farmers improved during the duration of the demonstration in terms of harvesting efficiency. Harvesting efficiency started from a low efficiency of 1.6 dry t/hr and increased every day to reach an average value of 2.2 dry tons per hour.

The total harvesting cost (including all the value chain steps) was to 58 €/harvested dry ton of pruning.

In view of a further improvement of the harvesting efficiency expected in future the total harvesting cost could realistically decrease further.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Since 2010, in the area surrounding Calimera municipality (Lecce) in Southern Italy the olive tree prunings are no more a disposal problem. A circular economy model turning agricultural waste into energy is running. It is the biomass plant called Fiusis fuelled exclusively with local olive tree prunings.

Fiusis is an example of how is possible to turn a low value agricultural residue into clean energy, promoting local employment while preserving rural ecosystems.

Essential condition was the huge availability of biomass, but not the only one. Even more than the necessary funding, the engagement of local farmers in the supply chain as well as the local consensus achievement were crucial to start up the initiative. The supply chain organization had a key role.

For these reasons in the framework of the AGROinLOG H2020 Project, Fiusis plant has been identified as a reference model in the organization of the new energy chain in the Fthiotida Region (Central Greece) where there are similar climatic and agricultural characteristics to the southern Italy.

Greek Project partners received first-hand valuable insights during technical visits at Fiusis plant. Technical parameters about the mechanical harvesting were assessed both in Italy and in Greece, where the shredder system was transferred. After two-years pruning harvesting carried out successfully, the basis for the growth of an industrial chain based on olive tree prunings valorisation have been set up.

7 REFERENCES

- [1] European Parliament Report on a 2030 framework for climate and energy policies (20132135(INI)); 2014;
- [2] VITO, Utrecht University, TU Vienna, INFRO, R.S.& P. Sustainable and optimal use of biomass for energy in the EU beyond 2020; 2017;
- [3] EU 2015/1513 ILUC Directive. Off. J. Eur. Union 2015, 20–30.
- [4] Picchi, G.; Lombardini, C.; Pari, L.; Spinelli, R. Physical and chemical characteristics of renewable fuel obtained from pruning residues. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2018, 171, 457–463.
- [5] Dyjakon, A.; García-Galindo, D. Implementing agricultural pruning to energy in Europe: Technical, economic and implementation potentials. *Energies* 2019.
- [6] Pari, L.; Alfano, V.; Garcia-Galindo, D.; Suardi, A.; Santangelo, E. Pruning biomass potential in Italy related to crop characteristics, agricultural practices and agro-climatic conditions. *Energies* 2018, 11.

- [7] Acampora, A.; Croce, S.; Assirelli, A.; Del Giudice, A.; Spinelli, R.; Suardi, A.; Pari, L. Product contamination and harvesting losses from mechanized recovery of olive tree pruning residues for energy use. *Renew. Energy* 2013.
- [8] ISTAT Superfici in produzione - dati in complesso 2019.
- [9] Gonçalves, C.; Evtugina, M.; Alves, C.; Monteiro, C.; Pio, C.; Tomé, M. Organic particulate emissions from field burning of garden and agriculture residues. *Atmos. Res.* 2011, 101, 666–680.
- [10] Monni, M. (ITABIA) In Puglia un modello di economia circolare che parte dagli oliveti. *Mondo Macch.* 2017, 5–6, 72–76.
- [11] Kougioumtzis, M.A.; Karampinis, E.; Grammelis, P.; Kakaras, E. Exploitation of olive tree prunings. Evaluation of an integrated harvesting demonstration in central greece. In *Proceedings of the European Biomass Conference and Exhibition Proceedings*; 2019.
- [12] Ufg, C. and D6.3: Flagship success cases update v1. 2017.
- [13] H2020 Rubizmo Project. Innovative Business Case: Fiusis (IT) Available online: <https://rubizmo.eu/news/view/a6e02690-6bac-4f1d-9381-4e74d445f63b> (accessed on Feb 13, 2020).
- [14] Suardi, A.; Latterini, F.; Alfano, V.; Palmieri, N.; Bergonzoli, S.; Pari, L. Analysis of the work productivity and costs of a stationary chipper applied to the harvesting of olive tree pruning for bio-energy production. *Energies* 2020.
- [15] Suardi, A.; Latterini, F.; Alfano, V.; Palmieri, N.; Bergonzoli, S.; Karampinis, E.; Kougioumtzis, M.A.; Grammelis, P.; Pari, L. Machine Performance and Hog Fuel Quality Evaluation in Olive Tree Pruning Harvesting Conducted Using a Towed Shredder on Flat and Hilly Fields. *Energies* 2020, 13, 1–16.

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9 LOGO SPACE

